

A study on hydrodynamic permeabilities of aqueous solutions of some alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides across an inorganic membrane of aluminium oxide

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Abstract : Experimental results for the measurement of hydrodynamic permeabilities of very dilute aqueous solutions of some alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides viz. sodium chloride, potassium chloride, magnesium chloride and calcium chloride through an inorganic membrane of aluminium oxide of known thickness are reported. The results have been analysed in terms of the methodology of non-equilibrium thermodynamics. The mechanical filtration coefficient, Lp and the rejection coefficient/membrane selectivity (σ) have been evaluated and the effect of concentration on these parameters also discussed. To evaluate activation parameters the hydrodynamic permeabilities have been determined at different temperatures.

Keywords : Hydrodynamic permeabilities, aqueous solutions, alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides.

Introduction

Variety of transport phenomena arise across a membrane when it is subjected to different driving forces^{1,2}. Some of these phenomena such as ion-migration, electro-osmosis, self-diffusion, hydrodynamic flow, salt filtration, streaming potential and current, and membrane potential, etc. occurring across the ionic membranes have been described by Spiegler³ applying the principles of non-equilibrium thermodynamics.

Survey of literature shows⁴⁻⁷ that now-a-days lot of interest has been shown in the electrochemical character of the membrane which plays a dominant role when transport of charge carrying species are involved. Since from practical point of view, a knowledge of the permselective behaviour of the membrane and its variation with electrolytic environment is essential, so in the present work hydrodynamic permeabilities of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations in water have been carried out because these cations play a vital role in biological processes.

Due to stable character and applications of inorganic membranes, an aluminium oxide membrane has been used in the present study for the determination of hydrodynamic permeabilities of some alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides and their mixtures in water. The main objects of the present study are to evaluate the mechani-

cal filtration coefficient, the rejection coefficient and activation parameters, which may throw light on the mechanism of transport phenomena across the aluminium oxide membrane.

Results and discussion

The permeability of a membrane depends upon the molecular size of the permeant, the pores of the membrane, the density and viscosity of the permeant, the state of aggregation of the liquid, the number of hydrogen bonds etc. None of the properties described above alone determines the behaviour of the membrane. So before putting a membrane into practical use, it is essential to know its characteristics, viz. effective cross-sectional area, equivalent pore radius and the electrical character of the membrane, which has been determined in the present case as follows :

Membrane characterization : The rate of permeation through a membrane under the hydrostatic pressure depends upon the effective cross-sectional area (A) and the thickness (l) of the membrane². An unambiguous determination of either of these quantities is difficult due to the complex geometry of pores within the membrane. It is however possible to determine the ratio A/l , the so called membrane constant, in terms of which the permeant

behaviour of any membrane can be expressed quantitatively.

For the membrane having 'n' pores of equivalent radius 'r', the effective cross-sectional area 'A' through which permeation occurs is $n\pi r^2$. The electrical conductance 'K' of the membrane equilibrated with a permeant having specific conductance 'k' is given by the following relation⁸ :

$$K = n\pi r^2 \times k/l = (A/l) \times k \quad (1)$$

so that the membrane constant can be written as :

$$K/k = A/l \quad (2)$$

This constant is a characteristic parameter of the membrane and is independent of the nature of the permeating liquid, as long as the interaction between the permeant and membrane matrix is not strong enough to alter its equivalent pore radius⁸. The average pore radius can be evaluated from the following relation⁹ :

$$\left(\frac{J_v}{\Delta P}\right)_{\Delta\pi=0} = \frac{n\pi r^4}{8\eta l} = \frac{n\pi r^2 \times r^2}{l \times 8\eta} = \frac{A}{l} \times \frac{r^2}{8\eta}$$

$$\therefore r = \left(\frac{8\eta (J_v / \Delta P)_{\Delta\pi=0}}{A / l}\right)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where η is the viscosity of the permeant, J_v the volume flow, ΔP the pressure difference and $\Delta\pi$ the osmotic pressure difference.

The values of equivalent pore radius and other characteristics ascertained from hydrodynamic permeability for different solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides in water, are given in Table 1. It is evident from the results that the value of the membrane constant

(A/l) is fairly constant for all the binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides and is thus in accordance with the findings of Singh *et al.*⁸. In other words, the membrane constant is a characteristic of membrane only and is independent of the nature of the permeating liquid.

It is also clear from Table 1 that the equivalent pore radius decreases continuously with the increase in concentration of individual electrolyte and mixed electrolytes in water i.e. in binary as well as ternary systems at 298 K. These results suggest that all the alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides form cross-links at the walls of the pores of inorganic membrane of aluminium oxide thereby resulting in the decrease of equivalent pore radius. The equivalent pore radius is different for different permeating solutions indicating thereby that the equivalent pore radius is not the characteristic property of the membrane only but it is seriously influenced by the nature of the permeating fluid. Now if we compare the values of equivalent pore radius determined for binary aqueous solutions and the ternary solutions, it may be inferred that the equivalent pore radius further decreases in magnitude on the addition of 0.1 *m* potassium chloride, for a particular concentration of sodium chloride, whereas its magnitude is increased on the addition of 0.1 *m* magnesium chloride to a particular concentration of calcium chloride in water at 298 K. In other words, these results indicate that the cross-linking at the walls of the pores of the membrane is increased on the addition of potassium chloride while the reverse is true on the addition of magnesium chloride.

The permeability/filtration coefficient (Lp) :

The permeability coefficient, L_p , is related to pressure difference and is a measure of complexity of the

Table 1. Membrane characteristics ascertained from hydrodynamic permeability data for different binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides at 298 K

Concentration (<i>m</i>) (mol kg ⁻¹)	Conductance $K \times 10^4$ (Ω^{-1})	Specific conductance $k \times 10^4$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	Membrane constant A/l (cm)	Pore radius $r \times 10^5$ (cm)
Sodium chloride				
0.005	2.16	5.70	0.380	7.31
0.007	2.78	7.26	0.383	7.21
0.010	4.07	10.60	0.384	7.19
0.030	4.73	12.30	0.385	7.09
0.050	6.14	15.80	0.389	6.92
0.070	8.61	22.24	0.387	6.86
0.100	10.92	28.30	0.386	6.63

Table-1 (contd.)

Potassium chloride				
0.005	2.96	7.33	0.383	7.38
0.007	3.25	8.44	0.385	7.31
0.010	4.48	11.60	0.387	7.20
0.030	5.92	15.23	0.389	7.12
0.050	7.00	18.20	0.385	7.03
0.070	7.89	20.50	0.385	6.98
0.100	10.40	27.30	0.381	6.87
Magnesium chloride				
0.005	3.63	9.60	0.379	7.08
0.007	4.58	12.00	0.382	7.02
0.010	6.39	16.60	0.385	6.92
0.030	7.16	18.70	0.383	6.88
0.050	8.66	22.40	0.387	6.77
0.070	10.62	27.30	0.389	6.63
0.100	12.54	32.20	0.386	6.58
Calcium chloride				
0.005	3.99	10.40	0.384	6.96
0.007	4.63	12.20	0.380	6.94
0.010	6.19	16.23	0.382	6.89
0.030	7.24	18.70	0.387	6.74
0.050	8.36	21.50	0.389	6.63
0.070	10.06	26.20	0.384	6.57
0.100	12.34	32.40	0.381	6.49
Sodium chloride in 0.1 <i>m</i> potassium chloride				
0.005	9.82	25.70	0.382	7.08
0.007	11.14	29.00	0.384	7.01
0.010	11.93	31.00	0.385	6.94
0.030	12.84	33.20	0.387	6.84
0.050	13.42	34.50	0.389	6.69
0.070	14.28	37.30	0.383	6.60
0.100	15.71	40.40	0.389	6.52
Calcium chloride in 0.1 <i>m</i> magnesium chloride				
0.005	10.64	28.00	0.380	7.18
0.007	11.19	29.30	0.382	7.17
0.010	11.40	29.70	0.384	7.10
0.030	12.81	33.10	0.387	7.00
0.050	13.92	35.90	0.388	6.93
0.070	14.89	38.70	0.385	6.90
0.100	15.25	39.20	0.389	6.84

membrane. In order to verify if any difference of concentration exists across the membrane, measurement of density, viscosity and refractive index were made before and after the experiment. It was found that no significant change occurred in these properties.

The thermodynamic relation for the volume flow (J_v)

as a function of applied pressure difference (ΔP) and osmotic pressure difference ($\Delta\pi$) across the membrane is given by¹⁰ :

$$J_v = L_p \Delta P - \sigma L_p \Delta\pi \quad (4)$$

here the symbols have their usual significance.

Fig. 1. Schematic set up of the apparatus

It is convenient to determine the filtration coefficient L_p at $\Delta\pi = 0$ i.e. at equal concentrations of the electrolyte on both the sides of membrane so that expression (4) can be written as follows :

$$L_p = (J_v / \Delta P)_{\Delta\pi=0} \quad (5)$$

The experiments show that the volume transported per unit time is linearly proportional to the pressure head for all the binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides at 298 K. A sample plot for different concentrations of sodium chloride in 0.1 *m* potassium chloride at 298 K is shown in Fig. 2.

The permeability coefficient ' L_p ' has been estimated from the slopes of the linear plots of J_v versus ΔP for the different binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides at 298 K. The variation of L_p with concentration, for the different binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides was also studied and the corresponding values of L_p are given in Table 2. It is clear from Table 2 that L_p decreases with increase of concentration and is different for various solutions, showing that L_p is a characteristic of the membrane as well as that of the permeating fluid. If we compare the permeability results of binary

and ternary systems of sodium chloride and calcium chloride it may be concluded that the addition of small amount (0.1 *m*) of potassium chloride to a particular concentration of sodium chloride in water lowers the permeability while the addition of 0.01 *M* magnesium chloride to a particular concentration of calcium chloride enhances the permeability.

The rejection or coupling coefficient (σ) : The coupling coefficient (σ) was estimated from the relation¹¹ :

$$J'_v = L_p' (\Delta P' - \sigma \Delta\pi) \quad (6)$$

Since $\Delta\pi = RT \Delta C$, the relation (6) can also be written as :

$$J'_v = L_p' (\Delta P' - \sigma RT \Delta C) \quad (7)$$

where J'_v is the resultant or net volume flow, L_p' is the permeability coefficient, R the gas constant, T the absolute temperature and ΔC the concentration difference across the membrane. According to relation (7), the plots of J'_v versus $\Delta P'$ should be a straight line and it has been found to be so as shown in Fig. 3 (a sample plot for various concentrations of calcium chloride in 0.1 *m* magnesium chloride at 298 K). The coefficient L_p' is estimated from the slope of straight line. The values of L_p' thus estimated are given in Table 3. If the hydrostatic pressure

Table-2 (contd.)

0.010	2.52	2.56
0.030	2.42	2.50
0.050	2.34	2.43
0.070	2.25	2.33
0.100	2.16	2.25
	Sodium chloride in 0.1 m potassium chloride	Calcium chloride in 0.1 m magnesium chloride
0.005	2.80	2.67
0.007	2.63	2.66
0.010	2.58	2.62
0.030	2.51	2.55
0.050	2.41	2.49
0.070	2.37	2.43
0.100	2.27	2.40

Fig. 2. Plots of J_v vs ΔP for various concentrations of sodium chloride in 0.1 m potassium chloride at 298 K.

Table 2. Mechanical filtration coefficient (L_p) for various binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides at 298 K

Concentration m (mol/kg)	Filtration coefficient $L_p \times 10^9$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	
	Sodium chloride	Potassium chloride
0.005	2.84	2.92
0.007	2.79	2.88
0.010	2.76	2.81
0.030	2.70	2.75
0.050	2.60	2.65
0.070	2.53	2.60
0.100	2.35	2.49
	Calcium chloride	Magnesium chloride
0.005	2.58	2.66
0.007	2.56	2.63

Fig. 3. Plots of J'_v vs $\Delta P'$ for various concentration of calcium chloride in 0.1 m magnesium chloride at 298 K.

across the membrane is kept constant i.e. $\Delta P' = 0$, then eq. (7) can be written as :

$$(J'_v)_{\Delta P'=0} = -\sigma L_p' RT \Delta C$$

or

$$\sigma = -[J_v' / Lp' RT\Delta C]_{\Delta P=0} \quad (8)$$

The negative sign indicates that the hydrostatic and osmotic forces act in opposite directions. The values of σ so determined from relation (8), for different aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides are also recorded in Table 3.

The rejection coefficient (σ) is a measure of mem-

Table 3. Permeability data and rejection coefficient (σ) for various concentration differences (ΔC) for different binary and ternary aqueous solutions across the membrane at 298 K

ΔC (m) (mol/kg)	$Lp' \times 10^9$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	$\sigma \times 10^6$
Sodium chloride		
0.005	2.40	1.04
0.007	2.32	0.77
0.010	2.30	0.56
0.030	2.22	0.21
0.050	2.14	0.13
0.070	2.07	0.10
0.100	1.98	0.07
Potassium chloride		
0.005	2.66	0.97
0.007	2.60	0.73
0.010	2.55	0.55
0.030	2.50	0.19
0.050	2.44	0.11
0.070	2.38	0.08
0.100	2.29	0.06
Calcium chloride		
0.005	2.17	0.78
0.007	2.10	0.60
0.010	2.02	0.45
0.030	1.99	0.26
0.050	1.93	0.16
0.070	1.89	0.09
0.100	1.84	0.08
Magnesium chloride		
0.005	2.40	1.91
0.007	2.34	1.40
0.010	2.26	1.00
0.030	2.22	0.34
0.050	2.16	0.22
0.070	2.07	0.16
0.100	2.01	0.11
Sodium chloride in 0.1 M potassium chloride		
0.005	2.27	1.48

Table-3 (contd.)

0.007	2.21	1.09
0.010	2.15	0.80
0.030	2.07	0.27
0.050	2.01	0.16
0.070	1.93	0.12
0.100	1.85	0.09
Calcium chloride in 0.1 M magnesium chloride		
0.005	1.94	1.12
0.007	1.90	0.88
0.010	1.86	0.67
0.030	1.81	0.23
0.050	1.75	0.15
0.070	1.70	0.11
0.100	1.65	0.08

brane selectivity and according to Staverman¹² when $\sigma = 1$, all the solute is rejected by the membrane, while $\sigma < 1$ means a part of solute passes through the membrane. In terms of velocities of solute and solvent, σ can be interpreted as follows : when $\sigma = 1$, the velocity of the solute is zero, meaning thereby that the solute cannot cross the membrane, and when $\sigma = 0$ the solute and solvent move at equal rates through the membrane. According to pore model¹³ the rejection coefficient is known as the coupling coefficient, measuring the coupling between the total volume flux and the solute transmission. As the value of σ tends towards zero, the coupling increases and when σ becomes equal to zero, the coupling is complete. It is clear from Table 3 that the value of σ is very small (i.e. of the order of 10^{-6}) and it further decreases with the increase in concentration difference of a particular electrolyte, for binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides at 298 K, suggesting that there is no rejection of the electrolyte by the inorganic membrane of aluminium oxide.

Activation parameters : The hydrodynamic permeability of fluids through porous media varies exponentially with temperature¹⁴ and is characterized in terms of activation energy¹⁵. In order to obtain activation energy and hence the free energy of activation, the hydrodynamic permeabilities, for various binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides were determined at different temperatures.

The compatibility of equation

$$(J_v)_{\Delta\pi=0} = Lp \Delta P \quad (9)$$

with Poissuille's law requires that

$$Lp = \pi \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} r_i^4 / 8\eta l \quad (10)$$

where 'r' is the radius of the i-th capillary, 'n' the number of capillaries or pores in the membrane, η the viscosity of the permeant and 'l' the thickness of the membrane. The variation of η of a liquid with temperature can be expressed as an activation process

$$\eta = A.e^{En/RT} \quad (11)$$

where A is a constant and En the activation energy. Substituting eq. (11) into (10) and taking logarithms it is found that

$$\log Lp = K - En/RT \quad (12)$$

where

$$K = \log \pi \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} r_i^4 / 8\eta l = \text{Constant} \quad (13)$$

According to relation (12), a plot of $\log Lp$ versus $1/T$

should be linear and the same has been found to be true. The slope of the linear plot gives the value of activation energy (En), which can be taken as enthalpy of activation (ΔH) for viscous flow across the membrane and these values for various solutions are given in Table 4.

The entropy of activation can be estimated from the Eyring rate equation¹⁴,

$$\eta = \frac{Nh}{V} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S}{R}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\Delta H}{RT}\right) \quad (14)$$

where η is the viscosity of permeant, N the Avogadro number, h the Plank constant, V the molar volume of permeant and ΔS the entropy of activation. Eq. (14) can also be arranged as :

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H}{T} + R \log (Nh/V\eta) \quad (15)$$

The values of ΔS for different systems, obtained from relation (15) at 298 K are also recorded in Table 4. It is clear from Table 4 that the values of ΔS are negative for

Table 4. Activation parameters for binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides

Concentration <i>m</i> (mol/kg)	Energy of activation ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Entropy of activation ΔS_{298} (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Free energy of activation ΔG_{298} (kJ mol ⁻¹)
0.1	6.48	Sodium chloride	26.25
		-88.07	
0.1	5.49	Potassium chloride	23.11
		-77.52	
0.1	7.31	Calcium chloride	13.81
		-46.33	
0.1	6.49	Magnesium chloride	9.73
		-32.65	
		Sodium chloride in 0.1 <i>m</i> potassium chloride	
0.005	6.16	-87.90	26.20
0.007	7.98	-87.89	26.19
0.010	7.96	-86.78	25.87
0.030	7.98	-87.65	26.13
0.050	8.34	-87.54	26.09
0.070	7.98	-87.43	26.06
0.100	8.48	-87.31	26.06
		Calcium chloride in 0.1 <i>m</i> magnesium chloride	
0.005	6.31	-47.03	14.02
0.007	6.31	-46.91	13.98
0.010	7.15	-46.80	13.95
0.030	7.23	-46.56	13.88
0.050	7.15	-46.35	13.82
0.070	7.15	-46.09	13.74
0.100	7.31	-45.91	13.69

the binary and ternary aqueous solutions of alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides. The negative sign associated with ΔS shows that the hydrodynamic flow process through the membrane has strong electrostatic interactions between the ions and walls of the membrane. This may be attributed to a state of high order during this transport.

The values of the free energy of activation (ΔG) were calculated at 298 K from the relation¹⁶ :

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (16)$$

and are also recorded in Table 4. A perusal of results shows that the values of ΔG are positive, meaning thereby that the flow across the membrane is not favoured by alkali and alkaline earth metal chlorides in binary and ternary aqueous solutions. In other words, it may be said that until an input force is applied across the membrane, the flow of the permeant cannot take place.

Experimental

Sodium chloride, potassium chloride, magnesium chloride, calcium chloride and aluminium oxide, used in the present study, were of AnalaR grade and used without further purification only after drying over P_2O_5 .

Double distilled water was used for preparing the binary aqueous solutions of sodium, potassium, magnesium and calcium chlorides and ternary aqueous solutions (water + alkali or alkaline earth metal chloride + 0.1 *m* potassium chloride or 0.1 *m* magnesium chloride). All the binary as well as ternary aqueous solutions of electrolytes were made by weight i.e. in molal (*m*) concentration (mole/kg).

Preparation of membrane : The aluminium oxide (Sd fine Chemicals, India) was swollen in conductivity water and cast in the form of a plug as described below :

The swollen material (10.00 g) along with small amount (5-6%) of an adhesive (araldite) was placed in a pyrex glass tube having a constriction in the middle and compressed mechanically at the site of constriction. It was left as such for about 24 h for complete setting of the plug (1.858 cm dia. \times 1.751 cm).

In order to know the directional character of the membrane for the permeation of water, the flow/hydraulic permeability was measured in both the directions at 298 K and the values were found to be same in both the directions thereby indicating the isotropic character of the mem-

brane.

Apparatus :

The design of the apparatus and its experimental set up is shown in Fig. 1. The apparatus consists of a pyrex glass tube of 30 cm in length having a slight constriction in the middle with an internal diameter 1.858 cm where the plug of aluminium oxide is set up.

Working procedure :

The experimental cell was filled with water and left overnight for equilibration of the plug. The cell was then thoroughly washed with distilled water under pressure gradient to ensure thorough cleanliness. The apparatus was filled by adding the conductivity water on one side of the membrane and then sucking it to the other side under a pressure gradient by means of a vacuum pump. This ensured the complete filling of the capillaries of the membrane. The apparatus was suitably mounted inside the thermostat, where it was allowed to attain a constant temperature (± 0.1 °C). The hydraulic permeability was measured by following the displacement of the liquid meniscus in a horizontal graduated capillary tube of known diameter with the help of cathetometer sensitive to 0.001 cm. The time was noted with the help of a stop watch graduated to 0.1 s. The experiment was repeated at other hydraulic pressure heads across the membrane. The flow of different solutions was also measured similarly by replacing water with appropriate solutions on both sides of the membrane. Conductance of the cell (membrane plus solution) and the specific conductivity of the permeant was measured with the help of a digital conductivity meter. The viscosity of each solution was measured with the help of suspended level capillary viscometer. For the evaluation of membrane selectivity/rejection coefficient (σ), one chamber of the apparatus was filled with a particular solution of the solute and the other with pure water i.e. either by filling the binary solution (water + electrolyte) or ternary solution (water + electrolyte + 0.1 *m* potassium chloride or 0.1 *m* magnesium chloride) on one side and water on the other side of the membrane. A pressure head of pure water was applied on the side of water chamber whereas the capillary was attached to the chamber containing solution to note the net (resultant) volume flow.

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